

The Optimum Aeration Time of Wastewater Treatment by Surface Aerators in Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University

Authors : Anat Thanpinta

Abstract : This research aimed to study on the efficiency of wastewater treatment by comparing the different aeration times of surface aerators in Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University. In doing so, the operation of surface aerators was divided into 2 groups which included the groups of 8 hours (8-0/opened-closed) and 4 hours (2-2/opened-closed) of aeration time per day. As a result of the study, it was found that the efficiency of wastewater treatment in the forms of DO, BOD, turbidity and NO₂- by 8 hours (8-0/opened-closed) and 4 hours (2-2/opened-closed) of aeration time per day of surface aerators was not statistically different [Sig. = .644, .488, .716 and .054 > α (.05)] while the efficiency in the forms of NO₃- and P was significantly different at the statistical level of .01 [Sig. = .001 and .000 < α (.01)].

Keywords : aeration time, surface aerator, wastewater treatment, efficiency

Conference Title : ICEBESE 2014 : International Conference on Environmental, Biological, Ecological Sciences and Engineering

Conference Location : Prague, Czech Republic

Conference Dates : July 10-11, 2014